

University of Bern - Institute of Geography

**High alpine winter discharge development
in Switzerland**

Bachelor's thesis

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Year of submission: 2024

Abstract

Catchments that experience full snow coverage in winter exhibit winter low discharge, where discharge remains at a low and constant level for extended periods of time. As climate change is affecting hydrological regimes in mountainous areas, analysing changes in winter low discharge allows for a better understanding of these processes. In this thesis, discharge measurements are statistically analysed to quantify changes in winter low discharge over a period of 40 years (1980-2020) and potential causes and consequences are identified. Models that project the change in yearly discharge cycles exist, but no such research has been executed on winter low discharge alone. To analyse whether these models can be used to project changes in winter low discharge, these models were also statistically analysed and compared to discharge measurements. Statistically significant changes in winter low discharge were found when analysing the data, albeit only in a minority of catchments. Winter low discharge amounts are increasing, and their duration is decreasing. The models were not found to be accurate enough to project changes in winter low discharge. As these changes in the functioning of water storage affect the availability of water further downstream, it is important to gain a better understanding of how climate change will affect these processes in the future.

Acknowledgements

I am extremely grateful to Prof. Dr. Schaefli who helped me with her valuable advice, suggestions and her great experience. Her unwavering support and optimism were of great value to my research.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Winter low discharge

Climate change influences hydrological processes in many ways. Amongst other consequences, it affects the discharge of streams through changes in precipitation and temperature (Muelchi et al., 2021a). These effects will be analysed in this thesis with a focus specifically on winter low discharge.

Winter low discharge is a steady minimum discharge that occurs in high alpine catchments during the winter months. When precipitation occurs in the form of snow in the whole catchment area, the water is stored and only a little portion released into the stream (Kohn et al., 2019).

The effects of climate change on discharge have been the subject of numerous scientific papers and other types of research. However, most of these were focused either on analysing the discharge's annual cycle or the prevalence of summer droughts, not winter low discharge.

One paper did analyse low discharge events but focused on the lowest 7-day discharge (NMQ7) and not winter low discharge as a whole. It was found that in alpine catchments, the NMQ7 values increased with the effects of climate change (Weingartner and Schwanbeck, 2020).

Other papers analysed the effects of climate change specifically on glacial catchments, but winter low discharge was not analysed as a specific factor (Huss et al., 2008; Kobierska et al., 2013).

In order to estimate the effects of climate change on discharge, hydrological models have been developed that project future discharge based on the RCP climate scenarios. According to these, winter low discharge is expected to rise with the effects of climate change (Muelchi et al., 2021b).

Comparing the model projections to physical measurements allows for a critical assessment of their accuracy concerning winter low discharge. No such analysis has been performed, so this will be one part of this paper. Generally, there is a lack of research on winter low discharge, climate change and the accuracy of current models. In this thesis, these subjects will be analysed in order to find results that fill this research gap.

1.2 Research questions, hypotheses, and goals

The main research question was: How does climate change affect the amount and distribution of winter low discharge in high alpine areas in Switzerland?

The following hypothesis was developed: The rate of winter low discharge in high alpine areas has increased due to climate change and will continue to increase. The duration of winter

low discharge will decrease due to higher temperatures causing snowfall to occur later in the year and snow melt to start earlier.

To more easily structure the research, five operational research questions were produced:

- Has the rate of winter low discharge increased or decreased since 1981? This research question can be answered through statistical analysis of discharge measurement data.
- Are there differing trends in different catchment areas? This can also be answered through statistical analysis and can determine if geographical conditions can change the effects of climate change.
- Are there other potential explanations for the detected changes? This research question aims to avoid determining correlations as causations.
- Do the detected changes match the existing models? What can be said about the accuracy of the models for winter low discharge?
- What are potential consequences that could occur when winter low discharge changes? This question can be used to gauge the importance of the subject.

The main goal of this thesis is to better understand the effects of climate change on the water cycle in high alpine areas. These findings can help in assessing the risk of natural hazards or in assessing the future availability of water. Agriculture can also be affected by changes in winter low discharge as increased discharge in winter means that there is less discharge in summer when it would be beneficial (FOEN, 2021).

The operative goal of this thesis is to gain more knowledge on the effects of climate change on winter low discharge. As relatively little scientific research has taken place around this subject, critically assessing the accuracy of existing models to project winter low discharge should help meet the goal of gaining knowledge of this subject.

Along diagrams and statistical analyses surrounding winter low discharge, the comparison of models and measurements should allow an evaluation on the usability of current hydrological models.

2 Study area

To select the studied catchments, multiple characteristics were considered. As the discharge measurements were provided by the federal office for the environment, only data for catchments in Switzerland were available. The model data (Muelchi et al., 2021b) was also only available for Swiss catchments.

Because winter low discharge only occurs when the catchment areas are fully covered in snow, a mean altitude of at least 1500m was chosen to ensure ample snow cover.

As dams, hydroelectric power stations or other kinds of infrastructure that can alter the flow rate would cause unnatural discharge patterns, any catchments that included such above the measuring station were not studied.

13 catchments met those requirements, more information about them can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical attributes of the analysed catchments (Federal Office for the Environment FOEN, n.d.)

Stream	Measuring location	Mean altitude	Area	ID
Simme	Oberwil	1641m.a.s.l.	344 km ²	2151
Simme	Oberried / Lenk	2347 m.a.s.l.	35 km ²	2219
Grosstalbach	Isenthal	1819 m.a.s.l.	44 km ²	2276
Alpbach	Erstfeld, Bodenberg	2205 m.a.s.l.	21 km ²	2299
Ova dal Fuorn	Zernez, Punt la Drossa	2327 m.a.s.l.	55 km ²	2304
Ova da Cluozza	Zernez	2371 m.a.s.l.	27 km ²	2319
Riale di Calneggia	Caverigno, Pontit	2003 m.a.s.l.	24 km ²	2356
Poschiavino	La Rösa	2285 m.a.s.l.	14 km ²	2366
Kander	Hondrich	1854 m.a.s.l.	491 km ²	2469
Verzasca	Lavertezzo, Campiòi	1651 m.a.s.l.	185 km ²	2605
Goneri	Oberwald	2383 m.a.s.l.	38 km ²	2607
Riale di Pincascia	Lavertezzo	1705 m.a.s.l.	44 km ²	2612
Rom	Müstair	2184 m.a.s.l.	128 km ²	2617

Figure 1: Swiss map with the analysed catchments highlighted. Source: Own work with vector data from FOEN and basemap from Swisstopo.

3 Data and methods

3.1 Discharge Data

The Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) operates around 200 discharge measurement stations in Switzerland. They are calibrated five to six times per year and an observer checks them for proper operation once per week (Federal Office for the Environment FOEN, 2024). In order to set up and calibrate a station, the discharge is measured at different water levels. This data is used to calculate a discharge curve that correlates the measured water levels with the measured discharge amounts, which can then be used to determine the discharge amount for any given water level. By using this method, the measurement stations design can be simplified to only include a water level sensor (Spreafico and Weingartner, 2005).

The data was acquired in a comma separated value format that includes daily average discharge rates in m^3/s . Data is available starting from 1980 for most catchments, with some featuring later starting dates.

3.2 Model Data

The model data that was compared to the measurements resulted from a study by Muelchi et al. that had been published in 2020. The study had used the PREVAH hydrological model, which is a model designed for complex catchments such as the ones analysed in this paper. It

accounts for all the major storage modes that affect discharge, such as snow storage, interception storage, soil moisture storage, unsaturated runoff storage, saturated runoff storage as well as snow, firn and glacier storage. The fluxes between these storage modes are calculated in order to model the resulting discharge (Muelchi et al., 2021b).

Three types of data were used as inputs: Daily temperature and precipitation data, geospatial information such as land cover and glacier projections and the CH2018 daily temperature and precipitation models. These account for the RCP climate scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5) and include up to 68 different model chains per scenario. To calibrate and validate the discharge models, the same discharge measurements as analysed in this paper were used. The resulting data for 93 catchments includes model data from 1981 to 2099 for each RCP scenario and its model chains. The data is available in daily, monthly, seasonal and yearly intervals. As only the months of December, January and February were analysed in this paper, the seasonal model data was used. The data is available in a comma-separated value format for each season, year, scenario and model chain with the discharge specified in mm/d (Muelchi et al., 2021b).

3.3 Methods

All statistical analyses and the creation of the diagrams were performed with the open-source statistics programming language “R” and the “RStudio” integrated development environment. To extend the basic functionality of R, the following plugins were used: “Openair”, “ggplot2” and “ggnewscale” allowed for more customisability in graphs. “Dplyr” and “reshape2” simplified bulk modifying data and “lubridate” was used to convert all timestamps into the same format.

The analysis is composed of two main branches. The discharge data alone was used to identify trends in the amount and the duration of winter low discharge by applying a linear regression as well as analysing potential correlations with geographical factors. Linear regressions were chosen to analyse the statistical significance of the above findings, as this is the recommended method to analyse the relationship between an explanatory variable and a scalar variable that is interval scaled (Universität Zürich, n.d.).

The discharge and model data together were first visualised to view the data and identify potential errors. Then, the mean square error was used to gauge the accuracy of the models and allow for comparisons in accuracy between different models and catchments. Finally, diagrams that allowed for visual comparisons between the measurements and the models were created by plotting the measurements and model data for 1981-2020 as well as the model data for 2021-2060 in the same diagram. Finally, the mean error and the mean projected change in discharge between the two periods was calculated to analyse the model’s accuracy.

As measurements were available starting from 1980 and up to 2020, the analyses were limited to this timeframe.

Figure 2: Flowchart showing the process of data analysis.

3.3.1 Discharge analysis

Discharge measurements were available in m^3/s and model data was available in mm/d . The decision was made to use the latter throughout this paper as mm/d is not affected by the area of the catchment. Thus, the first step was to convert the measurements to mm/d . After that, the data from December, January and February was extracted, its mean was calculated and inserted into a separate data frame that would be used for all following analyses.

To visualise the amount of winter low discharge and potential trends, a diagram showing the year in the x-axis and the yearly average winter low discharge in the y-axis was created for each catchment. Then, a linear regression was performed with discharge being the scalar variable and the year being the explanatory variable. The resulting trendline was added to the existing diagram. Further diagrams were created, and linear regressions were performed to analyse the effects of the mean altitude as well as the latitude of each catchment on its winter low discharge. Finally, a linear regression was used to analyse the effects of the mean altitude of each catchment on the slope of the winter low discharge regression line calculated earlier. The regressions were considered statistically significant if their p-value was below 0.05 (Andrade, 2019).

For one catchment (2319, Ova da Cluozza in Zernež), the duration of the winter low discharge was analysed. The method chosen was to identify the longest period each year in which the discharge was within the 25% quantile of all measurements that year. A linear regression was performed to analyse the relationship between the passing of time and the yearly duration of the winter low discharge.

3.3.2 Model analysis

To visualise the range of the different model chains for each catchment and scenario, six diagrams were created per catchment. Time is indicated on the x-axis, while the average projected winter low discharge is indicated on the y-axis. For each of the three RCP scenarios, one diagram visualises the model data as a box-whisker-plot, while the other uses semi-transparent dots to show the same. A line graph was used to visualise the discharge measurements. This style was chosen as it provides a way to display the spread of the model chain outputs more distinctly and allows visual comparisons with the measurement data. The diagram displaying the model data as box-whisker-plots visualises the median, quartiles and outliers while the version using semi-transparent dots allows for easy identification of values that are close to each other.

To assess the accuracy of the models, the mean squared error (MSE) was used (Equation 1). It is defined as the mean of the squares of errors, with the errors representing the difference between the measurements Y_i and the model projections \hat{Y}_i :

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2, \quad (1)$$

where i is the time step and n is the number of available time steps.

This method was chosen as the MSE is a way to assess the accuracy of a projection when direct measurements are available. A more accurate projection will result in a lower MSE value (Holst and Thyregod, 1999).

The MSE was calculated using the seasonal mean of all model chains for each catchment and scenario. Calculating it separately for each catchment and each model chain would have allowed for a more in-depth analysis, but the resulting amount of data – thousands of MSE values – would have been too involving to analyse in this paper. The resulting MSEs for each catchment and each RCP scenario were used to deduce which scenario was the most accurate overall, which scenario was the most accurate for each catchment and which catchment had the most accurate model. The most accurate RCP scenario overall was deduced by calculating the mean of all MSEs for each one.

Finally, a set of diagrams was created for two catchments to visualise model accuracy. For each RCP scenario, the measurements, the median of the model projections for 1980-2020 and for 2021-2060 were displayed as line graphs. In these diagrams, the error between the measurements and the projections for 1980-2020 can be set in relation to the difference between the projections for 1980-2020 and for 2021-2060. If the error is larger than the projected change, the projection lies within the models' margin of error and thus the models are not accurate enough to project winter low discharge. These differences were also analysed numerically by comparing the error of the model projections between 1981-2020 and the projected change in discharge between the period of 1981-2020 and 2021-2060.

4 Results

4.1 Discharge analysis

4.1.1 Discharge amount

The trendline of the yearly average winter discharge exhibited a positive slope in all analysed catchments. The slope varied between around 0.003 and 0.01mm/d/yr, meaning that the trendline describes an increase in average winter low discharge of that number for each year. However, the p-value was above 0.05 in all but two catchments, so the trend in 11 catchments is not statistically significant (see Table 2).

Table 2: Results of the regression analysis between the timeframe of 1981-2020 and yearly mean winter low discharge.

Station ID	Trendline slope (mm/d/yr)	p-value
2151	0.0041	0.534
2219	0.0050	0.063
2276	0.0027	0.588
2299	0.0044	0.307
2304	0.0045	0.056
2319	0.0078	0.001
2356	0.0104	0.042
2366	0.0043	0.158
2469	0.0039	0.387
2605	0.0178	0.193
2607	0.0035	0.393
2612	0.0078	0.632
2617	0.0070	0.175

Looking at the graphs (e.g. Figure 3), large year-on-year variations in winter low discharge can be observed, but the regression line visualises the overall increase.

Figure 3: Mean winter low discharge of the Riale de Carneggia with linear regression line.

Potential correlations between winter low discharge, its trendline slope and geographical factors such as mean catchment altitude, mean catchment latitude found strong correlations in some cases, but no correlations were also observed (see Table 3).

Analysing the correlation between the mean altitude of each catchment and its mean winter low discharge, a statistically significant correlation was found (see Figure 4). According to the linear regression, for each 100m increase in altitude, the seasonal mean winter low discharge would decrease by about 0.07mm/d.

Figure 4: Regression analysis of mean catchment altitude and mean winter low discharge.

No statistically significant correlation was found between the latitude of a catchment and its mean winter discharge (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Regression analysis of catchment latitude and mean winter low discharge.

Analysing the correlation between mean winter discharge and the trendline slope of changes in winter low discharge showed no statistically significant effect (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Regression analysis of trendline slope and mean winter low discharge.

The correlation between the mean altitude of a catchment and its trendline slope was also not found to be statistically significant (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Regression analysis of mean catchment altitude and trendline slope.

A statistically significant correlation was found between the latitude of a catchment and its regression line slope (see Figure 8). Higher numbers in latitude, meaning that the catchment is located further north, correlate with a lower regression line slope indicating that winter low discharge is increasing more slowly. The regression indicates that for each 100km that a station is located further north, its winter low discharge would increase by 0.01093mm/d less each year.

Figure 8: Regression analysis of catchment latitude and regression line slope.

Table 3: Results of the regression analysis for mean winter low discharge or regression line slope and other variables. Source:

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Trendline slope	p-value
Winter low discharge	Mean catchment altitude	-0.0008	0.0015
Winter low discharge	Station latitude	-1.411x10 ⁻⁶	0.7132
Winter low discharge	WLD trendline slope	5.1316	0.8175
WLD trendline slope	Mean catchment altitude	-3.389x10 ⁻⁶	0.4144
WLD trendline slope	Station latitude	-1.093x10 ⁻⁷	0.0205

4.1.2 Duration of winter low discharge

The number of consecutive days with discharge below the 25% quantile decreased between 1980 and 2020. Large fluctuations can be observed, but years with very few days in that quantile occurred only in the second half of the timeframe. The trendline exhibits a clear downward slope of -2.5, so in the regression, the duration of winter low discharge got shorter by two and a half days each year. The regression is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000175. As indicated in the graph by the interrupted line around 2005, part of the discharge data had to be removed from the analysis as the same value was measured over long amounts of time, pointing to a physical problem with the sensor.

Figure 9: Yearly duration of winter low discharge with regression line of the Ova da Cluozza in Zernež.

4.2 Model analysis

The first part of the model analysis resulted in plots that allow for visual comparison between the modelled discharge and the actual measured discharge for each catchment and climate scenario. They will be interpreted later in the discussion.

Figure 10: Plot of yearly mean winter discharge and all model iterations for RCP 2.6. Ova dal Fuorn, Zernez. Source:

The mean square error was overall lowest for models based on the RCP2.6 climate scenario and highest for models based on the RCP4.5 scenario. Catchment 2304 had the overall lowest mean square error, meaning that the models were most accurate in projecting its discharge while models of catchment 2612 exhibited the highest mean square error.

Table 4: Mean square error for the mean model projections and measurements from 1981-2020 for all catchments and RCP scenarios.

Catchment ID	MSE RCP2.6	MSE RCP4.5	MSE RCP8.5	Mean
2151	0.8269	0.9461	0.9706	0.9145
2219	0.4291	0.4386	0.4478	0.4385
2276	0.8719	0.8973	1.0203	0.9298
2299	0.9116	0.9477	1.0514	0.9703
2304	0.0889	0.0902	0.0907	0.0899
2319	0.1267	0.1278	0.1249	0.1265
2356	2.2181	2.4950	2.1363	2.2831
2366	0.4134	0.4401	0.4152	0.4229
2469	0.6398	0.6573	0.6848	0.6607
2605	2.6186	3.3050	2.7789	2.9008
2607	0.3130	0.3254	0.3339	0.3241
2612	3.5712	4.9709	4.1147	4.2189
2617	0.1328	0.1318	0.1336	0.1327
Mean	1.0125	1.2133	1.1002	

Discharge of the Ova da Cluozza in Zernez (2319)
Measurements vs Models RCP 4.5

Figure 11: Comparison between mean discharge (1981-2020) and model data (1981-2020 and 2021-2060).

5 Discussion

5.1 Trends

The observed trend of increasing winter low discharge amounts over the last 40 years is consistent with the effects of climate change. Higher temperatures in winter result in more precipitation falling as rain instead of snow, snowfall starting later in the year and snow melting earlier in spring. As a result, less water is being stored in the form of snow and instead runs off, increasing discharge (Bavay et al., 2013).

The observed trend also matches earlier research by Weingartner and Schwanbeck. In their paper, the increase in NMQ7 values (lowest continuous week of discharge) and Q_{347} values (Discharge amount that is exceeded on 347 day per year) are consistent with an increase in winter low discharge (Weingartner and Schwanbeck, 2020).

However, a statistically significant effect could only be observed in two of the analysed catchments. One potential reason could be the large year-to-year variations in discharge. One way to prevent this could be analysing the mean of several years of winter discharge to even out some of the oscillations. Another potential factor could be the relatively short analysis timeframe of 40 years. Had earlier measurements been available, a stronger correlation might have been observed (Ioannidis, 2005).

The duration of winter low discharge experienced a drastic and statistically significant reduction in the catchment analysed. This reaction is an expected result of climate change as higher temperatures mean that snow will fall later in the year and will start melting earlier, shortening the time during which the catchment area is covered in snow. As winter low discharge requires a fully snow-covered catchment area, this will also shorten its duration. Furthermore, higher overall temperatures mean that temperature fluctuations above freezing are more common, interrupting winter low discharge (Bavay et al., 2013).

Choosing a different definition of winter low discharge instead of the number of consecutive days in the 25% quantile could influence the observed trend. With the chosen method, if a single day averages above the 25% quantile, the calculated duration of winter low discharge is interrupted, and the count starts at zero if the next day does meet the criteria again. As a result, false measurements that are too high could falsely shorten the durations.

5.2 Consequences

Current climate models project little change in yearly precipitation amounts. Increasing winter discharge thus means decreased discharge during the summer months. This effect has consequences on the availability of water for several use cases. In agriculture, decreased precipitation in summer can require irrigation to ensure productivity. This alone means increased workload and cost, but the reduced discharge in Summer can mean that sufficient water for irrigation might not be available at all.

In areas where soil permeability is low, the increased discharge in winter might not all be able to permeate and recharge the groundwater, running off on the surface instead. Together with the reduced precipitation and discharge in summer, this results in a net decrease of groundwater levels over time.

Drinking water is often extracted from ground water, so that decrease can also reduce its availability in the summer months. Conflicts around the use of the available drinking water can arise and priorities as to who gets to use it will need to be set in this case. The quality of drinking water can also be affected as relatively clean groundwater recharge from river discharge can dilute pollutants in the groundwater. A reduction in recharge due to less discharge in summer can mean increasingly polluted drinking water, which negatively affects people's health.

Reduced amounts of summer discharge can also negatively affect biodiversity in rivers. Lower water levels mean that the sun can increase water temperature. The abundance of organisms that are sensitive to this change can decrease and they might not be able to survive these changes at all. If rivers dry out completely for some time, they might get trapped and die. Overall, the observed changes can negatively affect biodiversity in water-based organisms.

All these effects can have negative economic impacts. If farming starts to require irrigation or becomes unprofitable, jobs can be lost, and the cost of food and other agricultural produce will increase. Reduced availability of drinking water can increase its cost as well as potentially hampering industries that depend on large amounts of it. Negative health effects due to polluted drinking water will result in higher healthcare costs, which the public will have to bear. Industries that depend on biodiversity in rivers, such as fishing, will also be negatively affected if it decreases. Finally, reduced snowfall in winter can negatively affect winter tourism as the main reason to travel to the mountains during this time is the abundant snow.

5.3 Models

Visually comparing the measurements to the models, a few conclusions can be drawn. It is apparent that the models cannot accurately project the year-on year variation in discharge. This is expected as the models intend to describe long-term effects and not short-term variations. In the catchments where the increase in winter discharge was statistically significant,

the models also correctly project a long-term increase in discharge, so they are accurate in that regard.

For the Simme in Oberried (ID 2219), the models projected strongly elevated values every five years. After consulting with the authors of the paper, it was discovered that this was an effect of including the projection of glaciers melting. They updated the amount of water stored in glaciers every five years with data from another projection. The result was that the water from melted glaciers was added to the discharge every five years, falsely increasing it. The authors had found a way to decrease that effect and didn't publish findings for catchments where the effect was extreme, but it had not been noticed for this catchment. Evidently, the model exhibits lower accuracy for highly glaciated catchments.

For the Simme in Oberwil (ID 2151) and the Ova da Cluozza in Zernez (ID 2319), graphs for each RCP scenario were created showing the measurements from 1981-2020, the model average of the same period and the model average from 2021-2060. Comparing the differences between the measurements and the models from 1981 to 2020 shows the error of the models. Comparing the models between 1981 and 2020 and the models from 2021 and 2060 shows the model's projected change in discharge. If the error is larger than the projected change, the model cannot be used to accurately project changes in winter low discharge. It clearly seems to be case for both catchments. All three lines often overlap each other and the difference between the models and the measurements is rather large.

A numerical comparison was done by subtracting the mean difference between the error and the projected changes for 1981-2020 and 2021-2060. If this value is positive, meaning that the error is larger than the projected change, the model is not accurate in projecting winter low discharge. If the value is negative, the model has projected a change in the correct direction that is larger than its error margin. As can be seen in Table 5, for the Simme in Oberwil, the mean model error is higher than the mean change projected by the model, so it is considered not suitable for projecting winter low discharge. In the case of Ova da Cluozza, the projected change is higher than the mean error, but only by a small margin. Both examples demonstrate that the current models are not accurate enough to be used for projecting winter low discharge.

Table 4: Difference between the model error and mean projected change.

Scenario / Catchment	Simme (2151)	Ova da Cluozza (2319)
RCP2.6	0.088	-0.021
RCP4.5	0.108	-0.032
RCP8.5	0.187	-0.020

6 Conclusion

Winter low discharge is a metric that directly corresponds to the process of water storage in the form of snow. Thus, analysing the effects that climate change has on winter low discharge can provide an insight into how water storage in high-altitude catchments has changed and may change in the future. As water availability and ecosystem functions are dependent on discharge during the summer months and thus on water storage in the form of snow, analysing potential changes and their effects can help future action.

The first operational research question concerned changes in the amount of winter low discharge and the hypothesis was that higher temperatures due to climate change would lead to an increase. A statistically significant trend that supports this hypothesis was found in 2 of the 13 catchments. In the other 11 catchments, the regression also shows an increase in discharge, but the effect was not statistically significant. Several potential reasons can be identified, such as the large observed yearly variation in winter low discharge and the comparatively short analysis timeframe of 40 years.

Differing geographical conditions between the analysed catchments did affect the amount winter of low discharge and its change over time. Winter low discharge was lower in catchments with higher mean altitude, which can be explained by lower temperatures inhibiting the melting of snow. The measured changes were also found to be larger in more southern catchments, which could be a result of increasing sunlight intensity in places closer to the equator and weather systems creating an overall higher temperature (MeteoSchweiz, 2021).

The observed trends in winter low discharge can be explained by climate change as its scientific analyses project changes that would cause these effects. Higher temperatures cause snow to melt more quickly and thus add to the overall discharge. As winter low discharge only occurs when a catchment is fully covered in snow, higher temperatures will shorten this period. Finally, climate change also causes increased precipitation in winter, which can also increase discharge (FOEN, 2021).

To quantify potential future changes, the current models would have to be adapted to accurately project winter low discharge. As the amounts are low compared to the rest of the year, even small inaccuracies mean that the models will be off target by large amounts. They are accurate in that they project an increase in winter low discharge but are not accurate enough to quantify the future extent of discharge.

The consequences of increased winter low discharge alone are part of a larger cluster of changes in water availability caused by climate change. A reduction in water storage capacity during winter means reduced discharge during summer. This negatively affects water availability when it is most needed, a problem that gets compounded by summer precipitation being projected to decrease as well. Ecosystem functions are directly affected as plants may not

receive sufficient water and rivers temporarily dry up. Economic implications are also expected – farming may require irrigation, increasing the labour intensity, thus deteriorating its economic situation. Decreased availability for clean drinking water can also have negative socio-economic consequences. Lower snow amounts and shorter snow cover times in winter can negatively affect winter tourism as well (FOEN, 2021).

All in all, climate change negatively affects a multitude of factors that decrease water availability when it is most needed and can thus harm the natural environment, human health and the economy. Taking appropriate measures, be it by reducing carbon emissions or by directly mitigating the effects of climate change, requires knowledge and understanding of the underlying systems. Due to the delayed onset of these changes and the fact that implementing any measures takes time, research needs to expand as early as possible – ideally now.

7 Outlook

Changes in winter low discharge provide a direct insight into how water storage in the form of snow is affected by climate change. Increases in discharge mean that less water is being stored and thus less water is available during warmer periods. The results of this analysis showcase what has already changed and how quickly change has progressed, but to project future developments, further research is needed. As climate change is progressing, being able to gauge its impacts on water availability is crucial, justifying further action.

7.1 Limitations and challenges

Finding and choosing suitable catchments for analysis resulted in relatively few catchments meeting the requirements as measures to control the flow of a stream are common and would falsify the results. Analysing more catchments would result in more robust findings.

Furthermore, the 40-year timeframe is rather short when it comes to analysing climate change consequences and combined with large year-on-year variations reduced the statistical significance of the results. Incorporating older data and reducing the effect of yearly variations should result in more accurate and significant trends.

As there is no mathematical definition of winter low discharge, the results of any scientific analysis will differ depending on which one was chosen. This makes comparisons between different studies or using existing data more complex or impossible. A universal definition would simplify future research in this field.

The models analysed in this thesis provided a large amount of variation, with many model chains for each catchment and scenario. This meant that analysing each model chain individually for each catchment was not feasible. Combined with the low absolute numbers of winter low discharge, the models were not found to be suitable for projecting future winter low discharge.

7.2 Practical applications

The results of this thesis represent a first step towards better understanding the effects of climate change on winter low discharge. The observed effects match and support prior hypotheses and research, which is valuable. Having trendlines that roughly project the speed at which winter low discharge increases can be used to gauge future consequences as well as support policymaking.

Drawing up effective policies to either prevent or mitigate these effects requires extensive knowledge about the processes involved as well as expected reactions to any changes. This thesis offers a perspective on winter low discharge that has not been previously researched, making it valuable in these fields. It highlights the need for preparation and action to ensure water availability in the future.

The fact that current models are not accurate enough to project winter low discharge is a useful conclusion, as it highlights that further research should be undertaken.

7.3 Future research directions

A potential way to identify more catchments for analysis would be to research the kinds of flow control used on streams. If measures are only taken during periods of high discharge, winter low discharge might be unaffected, and the data could be included in the research. As another option, some flow control measures might be simple so that their effects could be mathematically reproduced. This would allow for the unaltered discharge values to be calculated, increasing the available data further.

Expanding the timeframe beyond 40 years would be difficult, despite older data being available as methodical changes mean that older data cannot be directly compared. The results' significance could however be improved by developing a smoothing algorithm that reduces the effects of yearly variations.

Developing a universal, numerical definition for winter low discharge is another research path that could be undertaken. This could be achieved by analysing discharge data from various catchments and developing a formula that most accurately includes winter low discharge. The amount of discharge compared to yearly data or maxima, the duration of the event or the low variation in discharge over time could be used as potential factors in the definition.

Projecting future changes in winter low discharge requires developing and testing new models with higher accuracy. Limiting the timeframe used for training the models to only winter would result in models that are more specifically focused on winter low discharge, increasing their accuracy.

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Data availability and attachments

The RStudio code files as well as all the generated figures and the raw data are made available together with this document as a .zip file. The file also contains a readme file that explains the folder structure and how to run the scripts.